

A niche market of wound care products and emergence of nanotechnology – A short review[†]

Nirmla Devi and Joydeep Dutta*

Department of Chemistry, Amity School of Applied Sciences, Amity University Haryana, Pachgaon-122 413,
Near IMT Manesar, Haryana, India

E-mail : dutta_joy@yahoo.co.in Fax : 91-124-2337016

Abstract : Wound healing is a complex, specific, physiological, and biological process. Wound healing progresses through a series of tightly regulated, cascades events that starts at a time of injury and continues till recovery. In wound healing, a dressing material plays a crucial role. That is why selection of dressing materials according to wound condition is of paramount importance. Otherwise, acute wound may convert into chronic wound and thus, the normal function of wound healing cycle would get disturbed. This article has summarized information about various types of wounds, phases of wound healing, and wound dressing materials. In addition, it has also highlighted the role of nanotechnology in fabricating improved wound care products.

Keywords : Wound, wound healing, nanotechnology, wound care products.

Introduction

The advent of nanotechnology has provided a great opportunity to fabricate nanocomposite wound dressings that significantly accelerate the healing process. Nanoparticles possess many exciting properties such as strong adsorption, high surface reactivity, and small size ranging between 1 and 100 nm¹. Nanoparticles have a high surface to volume in proportion to their mass. An increased surface area of nanoparticle, typically enhances cellular and biological activity by mass compared to bulk material. The novel properties (such as antimicrobial properties, mechanical properties, etc.) of materials at the nano range have explored numerous opportunities for their tremendous applications in the pharmaceutical and biomedical field, especially in wound healing. A wound dressing protects the wound from microbial attack that is responsible not only for causing infection but also for delaying healing process, which in turn, causes a serious problem to public life². According to the literature survey, it has been known that there are numerous types of wound dressings available in the today's market. Depending on the conditions of wound and healing system, proper wound dressing material is needed in order to achieve complete healing³. Therefore, it may be regarded that one dressing

material can never be prescribed for all types of wounds. Selection of wound dressings plays a pivotal role in wound healing process because they not only improve healing but also manage infected wound nicely. Moreover, wound care products should be customized according to the nature's of wound that can significantly accelerate the progress of healing. Here, we have discussed about the types of wound and their various phases relating to progress of healing; wound dressings; and role of nanotechnology towards fabrication of new wound care materials.

Types of wounds and wound healing cycle

A wound is defined as the disruption of the integrity of anatomical structure and function subjected to its exposure to any factor. Wounds are categorized on the basis of various parameters namely level of exudates, microbial contaminations, layers involved, and tissue loss⁴⁻⁶. These are shown in Fig. 1.

Basically, wound healing is a complex process in which various cellular as well as biochemical components play a pivotal role in repairing tissue. Wound healing progresses through a series of interdependent and overlapping stages in which a variety of cellular and matrix components acts

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

Fig. 1. Types of wound on the basis of various parameters.

together not only to restore the integrity of damaged tissue but also to replace the lost tissue^{7,8}. The wound healing process is comprised of four overlapping phases : (1) hemostasis, (2) inflammation, (3) proliferation, and (4) maturational or remodelling. To have a better understanding, a schematic representation of different phases is shown in Fig. 2.

Progresses in wound care products from inactive to bioactive products (wound dressing materials)

A vast amount of research has proved that moist wound environment is conducive for quick healing. That is why scientists are greatly inclined to design advanced wound care products, which provide virtually all properties benchmarked for an ideal wound dressing. The moist wound environment enhances the healing process not only by preventing scab formation but also by providing ther-

mal insulation. On the basis of wound healing and nature of wounds, numerous wound dressings are found in the form hydrocolloids, hydrofiber, film, tulle, gauze, foam, alginate, hyaluronic acid, collagens, hydrogels, films^{3,9}, etc. In brief, wound dressing materials can be categorized into three heads : (1) inactive products, (2) interactive products, and (3) bioactive products. These are described as follows :

Passive/inactive products :

Gauze and tulle are the most common passive/inactive products used as wound dressings since the ancient times and are still, in use today. Nowadays, these types of dressings are available in numerous forms such as strip, sheet, roll, sponge, and pad. But there are some drawbacks of using these kinds of wound dressings because they damage the healthy skin at the time of removing, which in turn, is also painful to patients.

Fig. 2. Four phases of wound healing.

Interactive products :

The usage of interactive wound care products in the form of film, foam, and hydrogels is increasing significantly in the last few decades. These materials are transparent, permeable to water vapor, atmospheric oxygen, absorb large amount of exudates, and create good barriers against permeation of bacteria to the wound environment.

Foam dressing materials are made up of hydrophilic polyurethane or silicone. They are designed to absorb high level of exudate and create moist environment to prevent drying the wound surface completely. These dressings facilitate autolytic debridement of necrosis, and slough. These dressings are available in various forms in markets as pads and sheets¹⁰.

Hydrogels are semi solid systems made up of polymers and water. They possess high degree of water content up to 96%, which make them ideal dressings for promoting rapid debridement by facilitating autolysis of dead tissue. Poly(vinyl alcohol) and poly(ethylene glycol) are common polymers, which get cross-linked with natural polymers such as chitosan, dextran, starch, gelatin, etc., to form hydrogel. Hydrogel maintains a favourable condition at wound site that enhances the healing process without causing maceration. Here, it is noteworthy to mention that hydrogel-based dressings are not suitable for heavily exuding wounds¹¹ because the strength of these dressings is quite poor. The strength of hydrogel can be improved by adding nanofiller particles¹². The hydrogel is typically used in wound care products because it is similar to living tissue.

Films are transparent, extremely flexible, and adhesive. These dressings are used to cure the wound, burn, and those injuries, which heal without complication. A film itself can act as a barrier to control the growth of microorganism growth and also provide waterproof covering. The films are extremely useful as wound dressings for treating a wide range of wounds such as abrasions, lacerations, partial thickness wounds, and full thickness wounds.

Bioactive products :

In the last few decades, researchers have been putting more efforts in developing bioactive dressing products. These dressing materials are soft, non-adhesive, and efficient in delivering substance towards wounds during wound healing process. Bioactive wound dressing materials are developed with the help of numerous types of polymers

such as pectin, collagen, keratin, chitin, chitosan, hyaluronic acid, to name a few. Alginate and its salts are especially used for the treatment of heavily exuding wounds because when these dressings come in contact with wound fluid, they form a gel, which in turn, enhances the growth of skin epidermis¹³ and the dressings can easily be peeled off without causing any harm to healthy tissue.

Collagen is a most abundant natural protein found in connective tissue of mammals. It plays significant role in wound repairing due to its unique properties such as biocompatibility, and biodegradability¹⁴. Numerous types of collagen dressings are available in market and these are used for treating various types of wounds such as granulating wounds, partial thickness wounds, and full thickness wounds. A snapshot of collagen dressing used for wound healing application is shown in Table 1.

Chitosan has been extensively used in wound healing research, because it possesses some exciting biological properties including biocompatibility, biodegradability, cytotoxicity, antimicrobial activity, and non toxicity¹⁵. It is used in treatment of various kinds of wounds because it enhances the formation of fibroblasts, macrophages, cell proliferation, and epithelialization that facilitate the efficacy of wound healing process.

Influence of nanotechnology in wound care products

The emergence of nanotechnology may open up new path for the fabrication of wound care products, which drastically changes the existing properties of the wound dressing materials. Nanocomposite wound dressings not only improve the performances of dressings but also reduce the wound healing time. The nanotechnology has the potential to introduce many exciting and prominent properties in wound dressing materials in terms of antimicrobial activity, mechanical properties, heat resistance, etc. The nanotechnology has provided new opportunities for exploring the effects of biopolymer based nanomaterials in wound healing. A recent investigation indicates that polymer nanocomposite-based wound dressing can reduce not only the healing time but also increase the barrier properties against microorganism growth¹⁶. Recently, numerous investigations have been conducted to develop wound dressings by incorporating nanomaterials into polymer matrices, because nanomaterials due to their extremely small sizes increase the surface area, which can effectively enhance the mechanical strength as well as antimicrobial activity. The several nanomaterials such as copper, silver, titanium oxide, zinc oxide, etc., are used for

Table 1. Collagen dressing used for wound healing application

Products name	Active components	Form	Wound condition type
Catrix®	Bovine cartilage	Powder	1st and 2nd degree burns and pressure ulcer (I-IV stages)
BIOSTEP◇	Porcine derived collagen	Matrix	Partials thickness and full thickness wounds
Endoform™	Collagen and 10% ECM components	Foam	Traumatic wounds and surgical wounds
Collaguard™	Type I collagen	Film	Superficial and deep wounds
Biopad™	Equine collagen Type I	Pad	Acute wounds and chronic wounds
Helix3 CM™	Type I bovine collagen	Matrix	Burns, sores, blisters, ulcers and wounds
Stimulen™	Collagen and glycerin	Gel	Deep cavity wounds
Puracol Plus AG ⁺	Collagen and silver	Sheet	Heavily drainage wounds, surgical wounds and traumatic wounds
DermaCol/Ag	Collagen, sliver, sodium alginate, carboxyl methylcellulose and EDTA	Gel sheet	Abrasions, ulcers and full and partial thickness wounds
Collasate	Collagen and silver oxide	Gel	Non-surgical wounds, traumatic wounds, grafted wounds and donor site

Note : All products information was obtained from wound dressing' websites.

biomedical applications, especially in fabricating wound care products. Recently, Dutta *et al.*¹⁷ reported that incorporation of nanoparticles into chitosan/pectin nanocomposite not only improved antibacterial properties but also reduced wound healing time. Some other researchers also reported the preparation of polymeric nanocomposite-based wound dressings, which are described elsewhere¹⁸⁻²⁰.

Market survey of existing wound dressing materials

Dressing materials are usually used to cover damaged tissue at the time of skin damage to prevent the loss of blood, exudates, and to reestablish the integrity of the damaged tissue. Both synthetic polymers and natural polymers have been used so far to fabricate wound dressings, which are already available in the market. These dressing materials promote fibroblasts proliferation, collagen deposition, and also provide thermal insulation. In addition, they also prevent maceration, and also facilitate autolysis of necrotic tissues. A wide range of dressing materials^{3,9,21} exists in national and international markets for treatments of wounds and burns. A snapshot of wound care products available in national and international market is shown in Table 2.

Comparative study between normal wound dressings and nanomaterials based wound dressings

Since the ancient time, men have been using various kinds of wound products such as milk, herbs, vinegar, linen, tulle, and gauze for effective wound healing. These wound care products stick at wound site and damage

healthy skin at the time of removing. Normal wound care products such as Polyskin™, Cutifilm are not suitable for heavily exuding wounds. On the other hand, a few wound dressings such as Melolin, Band-Aid®, etc., may not prevent maceration. Some wound dressings such as Tegaderm²¹ may not be perfect for dry wound.

Therefore, an increased attention has been paid on the development of nano-based wound dressing materials to overcome the shortcomings associated with the conventional dressing materials. Nanotechnology is an innovative approach to prepare nano-based composite wound dressings. Incorporation of anti-bacterial agents/drugs in the form of nanoparticles into the polymer matrices for the fabrication of wound dressings can significantly enhance anti-bacterial activities of the wound dressings as a consequence of their strong interaction at molecular and cellular level that reduces the overall time span for wound healing. Recently, there has been a growing interest in incorporating silver nanoparticles, gold nanoparticles, etc., into the polymer matrices for the preparation of wound dressings. For instance, Acticoat 7, Curad®, Silverline®, Chitoflex®, Permacol™, Aquacel-Ag hydrofiber, Biobrane™, to mention a few are nanotechnology-based wound care products, and these are highly effective compared to conventional dressing materials.

Conclusions

This article provides necessary information about wounds; wound types; different phases of wound healing; wound care products; and role of nanotechnology in wound healing applications. In the recent past, there has

Table 2. Wounds dressing products available in national and international market

Product's name	Manufacturer's name	Base materials	Dressing types	Advantages	Disadvantages
Tegaderm™	3M Health Care Ltd.	Polyurethane	Hydrogel	Maintain moist environment and prevent scab formation	Not perfect for deep wound and 3rd degree burns
Hizel*	Embeem Inc	PVA, agar and carrageenan	Hydrogel	Good for wound healing and easily remove	Only suitable for normal fluids releasing wound
Reliheal®G*	Reliance Life Science Ltd.	Poly vinyl alcohol	Hydrogel sheet	Good for wound healing and provides a moist environment	Not suitable for heavy exuding wounds
Geliper™	Geistlich Sons Ltd.	Polyacrylamide and agar	Hydrogel sheet	It protects the wound for drying and reduces local pain	Not suitable for deep cavity wounds
Vigilon*	Bard Distributed Seton Health Care Group Plc	Polyethylene oxide and 96% water	Non woven pad	Easily peel out at wound site without damaging healthy tissue	May not suitable for wound release heavy fluid
Aguacel AG	Conva Tec	Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose and silver	Hydrogel	Prevent microbial infection	Not good for dry wound or covered with hard necrotic tissue
Amerigel®	Amerx Health Care Corp.	Polyethylene glycol and zinc acetate	Hydrogel	Enhance healing in ulcers, 1st and 2nd burns, pressure and cuts	May not suitable for sensitive skin
Atrauman®Ag*	Avante Chemicals and Pharmaceutical	Silver	Ointment	Help to prevent maceration and prevent microbial infection	Not suitable all types of wounds
NeuSkin-f*	Eucare Pharma. Private Ltd.	Type 1 collagen (Fish origin)	Sheet	Facilitates normal healing process and reduce pain	Not suitable infected wound and wounds with heavy exudation
Kollagen-M*	Eucare Pharma. Private Ltd.	Collagen (Bovin origin)	Sheet	Promote epithelization and not toxic	May not suitable for heavily exudates wounds
Comfeel Plus	Coloplast	Polyurethane and calcium alginate	Hydrocolloid	Dressing is water proof and protect from microbial infection	Not suitable for exposed muscle and bone
Melolin*	Smith and Nephew Health Care Ltd.	Poly(ethylene terephthalate)	Film	It is used to protect the dry wounds and open wounds	May not prevent maceration and inflammation to the surrounding skin
Intrasite Gel	Smith and Nephew Health Care Ltd.	Propylene glycol and carboxymethyl-cellulose	Hydrogel	Promoting faster debridement by facilitating autolysis of dead tissue	Only suitable for low fluid release wounds
Polyskin™	Kendell	Thin polymer film coated with hypo-allergenic adhesive	Film	Barrier against the growth of microbes	Only suitable for low exuding wounds
Promogran	Johnson and Johnson Medical	Collagen and oxidized regenerated cellulose	Matrix	Prevent from maceration	Not good for all types wounds
Cutifilm	Smith and Nephew Health Care Ltd.	Polyurethane	Film	Permeable to moisture vapor and oxygen	Material is not suitable for heavily exuding wounds
Opsite Flexigrid*	Smith and Nephew Health Care Ltd.	Polyurethane	Film	It is used to cure various types of ulcers and wounds	It is not suitable for deep cavity wounds
Mepilex Border*	Molnyycke Health Care	Polyurethane and polyacrylate fiber	Foam	Reduce maceration and absorb exudates of wounds	Not suitable for dry wounds

Table-2 (contd.)

Allevyn	Smith and Nephew Health Care Ltd.	Polyurethane	Foam	Create moist environment that enhance the healing process	Suitable for moderate to heavily exuding wounds
Duoderm	Conva Tec Ltd.	Polyurethane	Hydrocolloid	Provides a moist environment that improved the healing without causing maceration	May not suitable heavily exuding wounds
Tegasorb	3M Health Care Ltd.	Polyurethane	Hydrocolloid	Maintain an optimal moist healing environment	Not prevent maceration in heavily fluid releasing wounds
Kaltostat	Conva Tec Ltd.	Sodium and calcium salt of alginate	Alginate	Dressing is useful for bleeding wounds	Not suitable for dry or low exuding wounds
Medifin*	Medicare Hygiene Private Ltd.	Paraffin gauze dressing	Gauze	It is suitable for minor traumatic injuries	May not prevent maceration
Sorban	Pharma-Plast Ltd. Steriseal Division	Calcium salt of alginic acid	Calcium alginate	It is easy to remove without causing pain or trauma	Not suitable for dry or covered with hard black necrotic tissue
Sofra Tulle*	Hoechst Marion Roussel Ltd.	Paraffin, anhydrous lanolin and framycetin sulphate	Gauze	Prevent the wounds for drying	Does not stick at wound area

*Note : The products information was obtained from wound dressing' websites.

been a growing interest in developing nanocomposite based wound dressings because nanomaterials incorporated into wound dressing materials increase the anti-bacterial activity as well as reduce the wound healing time. In other words, due to increased antibacterial activity, the nanoparticles incorporated wound dressings reduce the chances of infection caused by microorganisms, which disrupt normal function of each phase of wound healing cycle. In addition, a list of various wound care products available in national and international markets is furnished as a ready reference, which may help entrepreneurs, researchers, and industrialists also to develop nanotechnology-based new wound care products for a niche market.

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